

Building confidence in a digital world.

Trusted Connections: A community based model for digital inclusion and empowerment

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Summary

The Trusted Connections project is a community based digital inclusion initiative designed to address persistent digital inequalities in the North East of England. Delivered through a partnership led by Durham University and in collaboration with Digital Safety CIC and a network of grassroots organisations: Let's Connect, Sacriston Youth Project, Auxillia Youth Services, The Newcastle Rugby Foundation, Pact House and BornGood, the project focused on four priority groups: young people, individuals at risk of becoming NEET, unemployed adults, and adults aged 55 and over. Its core aim was to improve digital access, skills, confidence, and agency through a relational, community-led approach.

At the heart of the project is a shift away from traditional skills-based models of digital inclusion towards a pedagogy of empowerment, which recognises that meaningful digital participation depends on trust, social context, and ongoing support. The project conceptualises digital inclusion through four interconnected pillars: access, digital literacies, agency and empowerment, and inclusive participation.

A key innovation of the project is its community-based mentoring model, where mentors are positioned as “meaningful others”, i.e., trusted individuals embedded within local communities who support participants over time. Rather than acting solely as technical experts, mentors serve as guides who help individuals interpret and engage with digital environments in ways relevant to their everyday lives. This relational model fosters sustained learning, builds confidence, and enables participants to develop both practical skills and critical understanding.

The project delivered a comprehensive set of interventions, including the recruitment and training of mentors, the establishment of community digital hubs, the deployment of a mobile pop-up digital lab, the development of an online learning and mentoring platform, and the delivery of a regional Festival of Digital Culture and Inclusion. All components were co-designed with community partners to ensure relevance, accessibility, and long-term impact.

Over a five-month period, the project met or exceeded all key performance indicators. A total of 27 mentors were trained, 5

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community digital hubs were established, and 113 digital inclusion sessions were delivered, reaching 369 unique participants across 1,380 engagements. Participants reported increased confidence, improved digital safety awareness, and stronger connections to their communities.

Evaluation findings highlight the effectiveness of the mentoring model otherwise be excluded from digital opportunities. The relational nature to act as trusted points of contact, providing personalised support environments. The model also generated wider community benefits and the ripple effect of knowledge gained beyond formal sessions as participants interact.

Evidence from participant feedback shows clear gains in digital confidence and skills. Older participants, who initially reported lower confidence, demonstrated particularly significant improvements, while younger participants showed consolidation and strengthening of existing confidence levels. In addition to technical skills, participants developed improved digital wellbeing practices, greater awareness of online safety and privacy, and a more critical understanding of the impacts and consequences of their digital engagement.

The project also delivered important benefits for mentors themselves, including enhanced skills, increased confidence, professional development opportunities (including accredited qualifications), and stronger community engagement. Mentors reported that the experience reinforced their own learning and enabled them to make meaningful contributions to their communities.

While the project achieved significant outcomes, its short timeframe limited opportunities for deeper, long term impact evaluation and extended capacity building. Findings suggest that future initiatives would benefit from longer implementation periods to allow relationships, trust, and learning processes to develop more fully.

A major legacy of the project is the development of a scalable blueprint for digital inclusion, centred on building “infrastructures of digital opportunity”. This model emphasises trust, community ownership, and sustained engagement, positioning digital inclusion as a collective, socially embedded process rather than a one-off intervention. It highlights the importance of combining expert

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knowledge with lived experience and embedding digital know how within trusted local ecosystems.

In conclusion, the Trusted Connections project shows that digital inclusion is most effective when it is relational, community driven, and grounded in trust. By investing in local people, strengthening community infrastructures, and fostering ongoing learning, the project provides a sustainable and adaptable model for addressing digital inequality and supporting meaningful digital participation.

Project overview

The Trusted Connections team and priority groups

At its core, Trusted Connections is a community focused digital inclusion initiative. It is led by a consortium of experienced and trusted organisations: Durham University, Digital Safety CIC, Born Good, and delivery partners: Let's Connect, Sacriston Youth Project, Auxillia Youth Services, The Newcastle Rugby Foundation, and Pact House. These partners bring together expertise from academia, digital safety, sustainability, and grassroots community engagement.

The Trusted Connections project focuses on four priority groups:

- Young people
- Unemployed adults
- Young people who are not currently, or at risk of becoming, disengaged from education, employment, or training (NEET)
- Adults aged 55 and over

By increasing the digital access, skills (basic and advanced), and confidence of these priority groups, and through adoption of a community-based mentoring model, the initiative aims to alleviate exclusion. Through strategic partnerships, the Trusted Connections project provides a scalable model for broader adoption.

The Trusted Connections team and priority groups

Project components

This project comprises six interconnected components and key performance indicators (KPIs):

1. Mentor network

A team of 25 trained volunteers to provide ongoing, peer-based support to help groups and individuals within community settings build digital confidence and close skills gaps through trusted relationships.

2. Community digital hubs

These physical hubs within community settings offer in-person support tailored to groups and individuals who are digitally excluded. These hubs play a vital role in building trust and ensuring digital accessibility with the support of the delivery partners.

3. Mobile pop-up lab

Developed by Digital Safety CIC with support from Durham University, this flexible, modular lab brings digital skills support and learning directly into communities.

4. Online digital skills and mentorship platform

This platform is the home of the mentor training package. It offers structured digital learning modules, advanced content, and access to a mentorship network, supporting long-term digital engagement and growth.

5. Upskilling of 300+ individuals

Through digital inclusion sessions delivered by trained mentors and hosted in community hubs (or with the support of the pop-up lab), the project anticipates that 300+ individuals will benefit from digital upskilling within the implementation time frame.

6. Festival of digital culture and inclusion

A regional event celebrated community learning, promoted digital participation, and shared best practices with stakeholders and the wider public.

All elements were co-designed with input from local communities, ensuring relevance, uptake, and long-term impact.

Project goals

The key goals of the Trusted Connections project were:

- To upskill **300+ individuals** in core basic and advanced digital areas, including digital literacy, online safety, content creation, critical media literacy, and digital identity for employability.
- To recruit and train **25 volunteer mentors** able to support learners in a sustainable, cost-effective manner.
- To develop a **digital learning platform** providing lasting access to content and support.
- To develop **community digital hubs** and a **pop-up digital lab** through which community-based digital inclusion can be targeted.
- To host a regional **Festival of Digital Culture**, increasing awareness, engagement, and momentum of digital inclusion approaches and initiatives.

Intended long-term impacts of the project included:

- Enhanced education and employment prospects for NEETs and unemployed adults as they gain digital skills required in modern workplaces.

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- Greater confidence and well-being in digital environments, especially for older adults navigating increasingly digital public services.
 - Reduced pressure on public services, as more citizens are able to use digital channels safely for self-service, communication, and support.
 - A sustainable, scalable, and evidence-based model that can be replicated across other digitally excluded regions in the UK
 - Evidenced based knowledge and policy recommendations, derived from Durham University's comprehensive evaluation, informing future digital inclusion strategies.

Research approach

The design and methodology of the Trusted Connections project reflect its core commitment to relational, community embedded, and empowerment-oriented approaches to digital inclusion. Rather than adopting a linear skills delivery model, the project was intentionally structured to cultivate trust, support context sensitive learning, and strengthen local infrastructures of digital opportunity. This section outlines the methodological principles, design decisions, and implementation processes that shaped the project, including the development of a shared conceptual framework, the recruitment and preparation of mentors, the creation of a flexible curriculum blueprint, the organisation of community-based delivery, and the evaluation strategy used to assess impact.

Advancing a pedagogy of empowerment

Conventional digital inclusion strategies have tended to prioritise access to devices and the development of basic digital skills, often framed through employability outcomes or narrow measures of functional competence. While such interventions remain necessary, they are insufficient for addressing the lived realities of digital disadvantage. A growing body of research in critical digital literacies argues that digital engagement is shaped by cultural norms, social relations, and institutional contexts (Helsper, 2020; Selwyn, 2004), and that meaningful digital participation requires more than technical proficiency (also see Costa and Oliver, 2025a). The Trusted Connections project draws on this scholarship to advance a pedagogy of empowerment, one that foregrounds informed agency, critical awareness, and the capacity to shape digital practices in ways that are meaningful to individuals and communities.

This pedagogical stance challenges deficit based models that treat learners as passive recipients of digital skills training. Instead, it views learners as knowledgeable agents whose digital practices are shaped by their histories, identities, and social environments (Costa and Oliver, 2023). Digital literacies, in this framing, are not static competencies but socially situated practices that evolve through participation, reflection, and dialogue (Costa and Oliver, 2025b). The project therefore emphasises relational forms of learning, where trust, continuity, and cultural understanding are central to enabling individuals to develop confidence and autonomy in digital spaces.

This theoretical stance directly informs the project's emphasis on:

- Community based and place focused approaches, recognising that digital practices are always embedded in local histories, values, and material conditions.

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- Co-creation and participation, ensuring that digital inclusion initiatives are designed with, rather than imposed upon, communities.
 - Trusted relationships, acknowledging that confidence, engagement, and learning are mediated through social bonds and institutional credibility.
 - Critical engagement with technology, supporting individuals to understand not only how to use digital technologies, but how those tools and environments may shape opportunities, create awareness of risks, and facilitate a wide range of experiences.

The Trusted Connections project operationalises this approach through a community based mentoring model that positions mentors as “meaningful others” rather than technical experts. Mentors are selected not solely for their digital expertise but for their embeddedness within local communities, their relational credibility, and their capacity to support others in navigating digital environments in contextually relevant ways. This model recognises that trust is a foundational infrastructure for digital inclusion. Without trust in institutions, platforms, or support organisations, individuals may remain hesitant or resistant to engaging with digital technologies, even when access barriers are addressed. By situating digital learning within trusted community settings, the project creates conditions in which participants can explore, question, and develop digital practices safely and confidently.

Addressing a persistent regional challenge

Digital inclusion has become a defining social, educational, and economic challenge in the United Kingdom, with the North East of England representing one of the regions most acutely affected by persistent digital inequalities (Clayton et al., 2013; Wilson-Menzfeld et al., 2025). Despite sustained national and regional investment in connectivity, digital skills training, and employability focused interventions, significant disparities remain in how individuals and communities access, understand, and meaningfully engage with digital technologies. These disparities are not reducible to technical deficits; they are deeply entangled with the region’s socio-economic histories, cultural landscapes, and institutional relationships. The Trusted Connections project emerges within this context as a critical intervention that reconceptualises digital inclusion as a relational, participatory, and community-embedded process.

The North East’s digital divide cannot be understood without acknowledging the structural conditions that shape it. The region’s long-term experience of industrial decline, labour market precarity, and spatial inequality has produced uneven access to opportunity and contributed to widespread mistrust in institutions (Forster et al., 2018; Warren, 2017; Telford, 2022). These dynamics influence not only whether people have access to devices or connectivity, but also how they perceive, interpret, and navigate digital environments. Digital exclusion is therefore not simply a matter of lacking skills; it is a manifestation of broader social and economic marginalisation (Helsper, 2017; Holmes and Burgess, 2022). The Trusted Connections project recognises this complexity, positioning digital inclusion as a social justice issue that requires attention to power, voice, and agency.

The Northeast of England thus provides a compelling context for our work. The region’s community organisations, youth projects, and local support networks play a critical role in mediating access to services, fostering trust, and supporting individuals who may be marginalised by formal institutions

(Robinson and Shaw, 2010). These organisations act as brokers of digital opportunity, offering spaces where learning can occur in ways that are responsive to local needs and grounded in shared values. The Trusted Connections project builds on this existing infrastructure, strengthening community-based provision and creating new relational ecosystems that support digital inclusion.

Development of a shared conceptual framework

In the initial phase, the project lead team developed a shared definition of digital inclusion that served as the conceptual framework underpinning the project. This was grounded in the specific needs of the North East communities our delivery partners serve, and can now be adapted and applied to wider contexts beyond the project.

Our definition of digital inclusion underpins a framework structured around four core pillars, which guided all project activities:

1. **Access:** Ensuring individuals have access to affordable, high-quality digital devices and inclusive support structures that enable full participation in digital life.
2. **Digital literacies:** Developing both foundational and advanced digital skills to support everyday activities, employment, and social engagement.
3. **Agency and empowerment:** Building confidence and trust in digital environments, enabling individuals not only to access content but also to create, collaborate, and participate actively online.
4. **Inclusive participation and support:** Fostering community-based opportunities that promote connection, learning, and overall wellbeing.

Figure 1 - Four pillars of digital inclusion as conceptualised by the Trusted Connections project

These pillars combined provide a holistic model for understanding and addressing digital inclusion. They reflect a deliberate move beyond narrow functional skills and towards a holistic understanding of digital engagement. Access remains a necessary foundation, but it is embedded within relational support structures that enable individuals to remain connected to guidance and learning over time. Digital literacies encompass both foundational and advanced skills, including digital safety, content creation, and critical engagement with online environments. Agency and empowerment emphasise the development of confidence, agency, and ethical participation, with agency understood here as the capacity to act meaningfully, critically, and ethically within socio-digital contexts. The inclusive participation and support pillar captures the socio-cultural and practical dimensions through which digital empowerment can be developed.

This framework is grounded in the recognition that digital inclusion is not a linear process but a relational and iterative one. Individuals develop digital confidence at different paces, shaped by their experiences, histories, and structural conditions. Standardised, efficiency-driven models of digital skills delivery often fail to account for these complexities, particularly for groups labelled as “hard to reach.” The Trusted Connections project challenges this narrative by demonstrating that these groups are not inherently disengaged but are often excluded by approaches that do not reflect their lived realities or provide the relational support necessary for sustained engagement.

Nurturing trusted connections: building a community-based mentoring model

Nurturing trusted connections requires rethinking digital inclusion as a relational rather than purely skills-based endeavour. In the Trusted Connections project, the focus moves from transmitting discrete competencies to cultivating sustained learning relationships that support the development of digital knowledge, confidence, and agency over time. Within this approach, mentors are not positioned as technical experts but as meaningful others (see Costa and Oliver, 2025a), i.e., trusted individuals who serve as digital cultural guides, supporting people to interpret and navigate digital environments in ways that reflect their lived experiences and align with the project’s core values and ethos.

Trust emerges through proximity, shared experience, and ongoing interaction, enabling mentors to draw on local knowledge, recognise constraints, and open up relevant pathways for engagement. As a result, mentoring becomes adaptive and embedded within community contexts, supporting not only practical know-how but also critical awareness and agency. By mediating digital cultural knowledge, mentors make visible the often implicit norms and practices shaping digital participation, fostering more confident and autonomous engagement. Digital inclusion is thus understood as a collective, place-based practice grounded in social connection and dependable support.

Central to this model is the idea of mentoring as a shared cultural practice rather than a one-to-one transaction. Mentors are embedded within their communities, modelling safe and ethical digital practices and supporting others through dialogue, observation, and collective engagement (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Marshall et al., 2025). This creates a generative cycle in which learners can themselves become mentors, sustaining community capacity and positioning the community as both the site and resource for learning (Costa, 2007).

To support this, the project has taken a deliberate approach to mentor selection, prioritising trusted individuals with deep community knowledge. This has enabled the development of a mentor network that functions as a relational infrastructure for digital inclusion. Mentors operate as community actors who support digital cultural knowledge in its fullest sense, encompassing technical, social, cultural, and ethical dimensions, while creating safe and supportive spaces for experimentation and reflection.

Through their ongoing engagement, mentors help bridge gaps between formal systems and everyday practices, translating abstract digital demands into meaningful, situated understanding. In doing so, they strengthen existing community knowledge while expanding opportunities for participation. The network not only supports digital development but also enables communities to shape their own forms of engagement, foregrounding continuous learning and reinforcing that sustainable digital inclusion depends as much on trusted relationships as on individual capability.

Recruitment of mentors

Central to the project's methodology was the recruitment and development of mentors. As detailed above, mentors were conceptualised not as technical experts but as “meaningful others”, trusted individuals embedded within their communities who could support participants in navigating digital environments in contextually relevant ways. Identifying these individuals required more than recognising their affinity with the communities they intended to support. To ensure a safe and informed approach to digital inclusion, it was also necessary to assess their level of digital knowledge before they could join the programme. This required the project to develop an appropriate method for evaluating this capability.

As a result, a significant outcome of the project was the development of a **Mentor Digital Literacies Diagnostic Tool** to support the mentor recruitment process. This practical resource enables mentors to self-assess their digital literacy levels and identify specific learning needs. Through automated feedback, the tool supports the validation and consolidation of existing knowledge while highlighting areas for further development. Crucially, the tool was designed with adaptability in mind, allowing it to be adapted and customised by organisations beyond the lifetime of the project, thereby enhancing the long term impact and sustainability of the Trusted Connections approach.

Mentors were selected based on their:

- advanced digital literacy skills, assessed through the Mentor Digital Literacies Diagnostic Tool;
- deep knowledge of local communities;
- relational credibility and trustworthiness;
- commitment to supporting others' learning;
- capacity to model ethical and reflective digital practices.

The emphasis on expertise was intended not to reinforce hierarchy, but to ensure that mentors could facilitate learning as an empowering process rather than a one-directional transfer of skills. However, this approach also meant that some individuals who were motivated to take on mentoring roles were unable to meet the criteria at this stage.

Despite this constraint, participation in the mentoring process proved highly valuable for those who were involved. Mentors reported increased confidence in their own abilities, the development of new skills, and a stronger sense of agency in their digital practices. Importantly, their involvement also provides new

opportunities within their communities, through the development of new learning relationships and resources that can continue to support digital inclusion beyond the life of the project.

Mentor training programme

A mentor training programme was developed and delivered to all mentors recruited to the project. The training programme was underpinned by the four pillars of digital inclusion developed within the project. It incorporated key aspects of digital literacies and ensured mentors were adequately trained and prepared to promote digital inclusion within their communities. The programme was organised into six thematic sessions:

1. Basic digital skills: Device access and use, internet navigation, social media general knowledge
2. Digital safety: Privacy, online safety, scam awareness
3. Digital citizenship and digital footprint: Online presence, employability, ethical participation
4. Healthy online relationships and wellbeing: Conflict management, boundaries, emotional resilience
5. Online confidence, community building and leadership: Moderation, facilitation, and community animation
6. Content creation: Audio and video storytelling, ethical representation, community engagement

These sessions were delivered online to all recruited mentors. Because of the tight project timeframe, and the geographical spread of community settings and mentors, it was not possible to deliver the mentor training sessions in person. To overcome some of the limitations of online delivery, mentors were encouraged to continue communicating and sharing ideas and resources outside of online sessions, and to contact mentor trainers outside of sessions. Mentors and community partners were very positive about the training package (see Findings). Nevertheless, if the project were to be delivered again, in person training would be a preferable option by those involved.

The mentor training programme led to the development of a flexible set of core **resources** by the leading partner (Durham University), in close collaboration with Digital Safety (the partner responsible for delivering mentor training). This set of core resources includes lesson plans, knowledge content, and learning activities, designed to be adapted for both mentor training and direct work with community groups. The creation of this blueprint was a deliberate pedagogical choice, recognising the need for teaching materials that could be responsive to diverse target groups, different levels of digital knowledge and practice, and distinct local contexts. Rather than prescribing a fixed curriculum, the resources were structured to allow adaptation, enabling mentors to tailor learning activities while remaining anchored in the conceptual framework of digital inclusion and shared principles of ethical practice and empowerment.

Given the project's conceptual grounding, this flexibility was deemed essential for learning that foregrounds and is open to diverse views and experiences, dialogue, and participation over standardisation of learning outcomes. This approach also aimed to enhance the appeal and legitimacy of digital inclusion initiatives within communities, ensuring that learning is experienced as meaningful, respectful of, and connected to lived realities rather than imposed through abstract or one fit all modes of delivery

Identification of community needs

While all mentors received the full mentor training package, the community-focused approach adopted within the project meant that community partners were empowered to identify the aspects of digital inclusion of most relevance in their communities and the four priority groups outline in section 2 of this paper: young people, unemployed adults, young people who are not currently, or at risk of becoming, disengaged from education, employment, or training (NEET), and adults aged 55 and over

Table 1 illustrates how the Trusted Connections project operationalised digital inclusion as a relational, participatory, and ethically grounded learning process, rather than as a linear delivery programme of digital skills. Across all delivery partners, access is positioned as a necessary but insufficient element of digital inclusion. Instead, access is consistently embedded within trusted, community-based settings and approached as a stepping stone towards safer, confident, and ethical digital engagement. Rather than treating access as a one-off provision of devices or connectivity, the partners' established community needs highlight the importance of sustained, relational support, support that enables individuals not only to access technology but also to remain connected to guidance, build confidence over time, and feel supported throughout their ongoing digital engagement.

Table 1 outlines a diverse yet complementary approach to digital inclusion across delivery partners, each addressing access, skills, and empowerment in ways that reflect their target audiences:

Delivery partner	Target Audiences	Access	Digital Literacies	Agency and Empowerment	Inclusive Participation and Support
Pact House	NEET; Young people; Adults 55+	Support access to digital devices and local digital services; drop-in employment sessions	Basic digital skills; use of QR codes; form filling; digital safety	Building confidence to engage independently with online services	Intergenerational and community-based learning
Rugby Foundation	14–16-year-olds at risk of becoming NEET	Access to platforms for CVs and online profiles	Digital citizenship; CV creation	Online self-presentation; digital footprint management; digital wellbeing; content creation (podcasts)	Inclusive, ongoing support through mentoring
Let's Connect	Community leaders	Access to moderated platforms and community spaces	Advanced digital safety; online moderation skills; ethical storytelling	Digital community leadership; online confidence; initiating online engagement	Ethical online community participation; representation of non-mobile individuals

Sacriston Youth Project	NEET; 8–18-year-olds; Adults 55+	Digital Café sessions (onsite) offering bespoke access and support	Digital safety (basic and advanced); content creation; CV skills	Content creation (podcasts); managing digital footprint	Intergenerational and community-based learning
Auxilia	Young people; Adults 55+	Digital Café sessions (onsite); access to creative tools	Digital safety; CV skills	Creative expression; content creation (podcasts)	Inclusive, ongoing support through community-based provision

The table demonstrates how the Trusted Connections project enacts a pedagogy of empowerment by integrating the four pillars of digital inclusion as defined by the project into coherent stepping stones for learning. Digital inclusion is framed not as a discrete outcome measured solely through skills acquisition, but as a process of becoming, i.e., becoming confident, critical, connected, and capable of shaping one’s digital practices in relation to one’s needs and contexts.

Findings

A comprehensive evaluation schedule was employed throughout the project. This ensured individual aspects of the project were evaluated: mentor training, session delivery, and the Festival of Digital Culture and Inclusion. It incorporated evaluation evidence collected from partners, mentors, mentor trainers, participants and members of the public attending the Festival. Evaluation activities included: a digital mentor assessment prior to mentor recruitment, attendance monitoring (of mentors during training package, of participants during session delivery in community hubs, of attendees at the Festival), mentor/partner/participant feedback forms gathered during each session and via end of project focus groups/questionnaires. Four focus groups with participants from the delivery groups were also conducted, and five case studies were developed. The full evaluation schedule is provided in Table 2 below.

Summary of findings

The project delivered a comprehensive programme of community-based digital inclusion activities. During the five months of the project, all KPIs (see section 2.2) were achieved or exceeded (discussed in more detail in subsequent sections).

“The project trained 27 volunteer mentors, developed a clear action blueprint, and launched both a digital platform and mobile pop-up lab, delivering 113 community-based digital literacy sessions that engaged 369 unique participants across 1,380 learning interactions.”

Headline findings demonstrate the achievements of the project:

1. **27** digital inclusion mentors were trained
2. **5** community digital hubs were created
3. **113** digital inclusion sessions were hosted across the five community hubs
4. **369** individuals were digitally upskilled during digital inclusion sessions
5. **1380** participations at sessions were recorded (many participants attended multiple sessions)
6. A **mobile pop-up lab** was created and deployed as needed
7. An **online digital platform** was developed and will be maintained and developed beyond the life of the project
8. A week-long **Festival of Digital Culture and Inclusion** with 10 separate events was hosted across North East locations
9. Participants and partners consistently reported **increased confidence**, improved **digital safety awareness**, and strengthened **community relationships**.

Table 2: Evaluation Schedule

Aspect	Date	Who	When	Activity
Mentor Training	Nov/Dec	Mentors	Pre-appointment	Digital Champion Assessment
Mentor Training	Jan/Feb	Trainers	Each training session	Attendance monitoring form
Mentor Training	Jan/Feb	Trainers	After each training session	Session feedback
Mentor Training	Feb	Mentors	Upon completion of mentor training programme	Feedback questionnaire
Mentor Training	March	Mentors	After project delivery	Focus group interview
Session Delivery	Feb/March	Participants	Pre-session and post-session	Pre-and post-session questionnaire
Session Delivery	Feb/March	Mentors	Each session	Participant attendance monitoring form
Session Delivery	March	Mentors/Partners	Post-sessions	Participant impact case study
Session Delivery	March	Participants	After project delivery	Focus group interview
Festival	March	Attendees	After each festival events	Feedback questionnaire
Festival	Feb/March	Organisers (DU or partners)	Pre-festival	Festival event registration
Whole Project	March	Partners/Mentors	After project delivery	Feedback questionnaire

Mentoring Approach

A key goal (and KPI) of the project is related to mentor recruitment and training. A total of 27 volunteer mentors were trained during the project following successful completion of the Digital Champion Assessment (developed for the project). 25 mentors enrolled to pursue a Level 3 certificate (funded through the project) enhancing their qualifications and experience as a result of the Trusted Connections project. A mentor training package was designed and delivered by the project team. Training enabled all mentors to work with delivery partners and host digital skills sessions tailored to community needs within community digital hubs.

Evaluation evidence from partners, mentors, mentor trainers, and participants demonstrates the overall effectiveness and satisfaction with the adopted mentoring model.

Mentor Training

In relation to the mentor training package, mentor trainers reported having successfully achieved session objectives and rated all sessions as 'good' or better. All partners said that the mentor training package worked effectively. Mentors described the training package as 'good', 'very good' or 'excellent'. Participant feedback also highlights the benefits of a mentoring model in enhancing digital skills and promoting digital inclusion.

Particular highlights identified by both partners and mentors included:

- Quality of teaching / training;
- Balance of technical knowledge and hands-on guidance;
- Opportunities for practical experience;
- Development of confidence, skills, and practical tools needed to act as digital champions in community settings;
- Provision of resources which could be revisited and which could also be adjusted to different age groups/needs;
- Development and provision of a digital platform hosting current, trusted and evolving resources to access and use moving forward (beyond the lifespan of the project and involving other potential mentors);
- An introduction to potential future participant groups and partners in the community (potentially widening reach of community partners);
- Pastoral support from deliverers, peers and other mentors;
- Ongoing check-ins, opportunities to ask questions, and access to support helped mentors continue developing after the initial training.

A consistent concern raised was that the sessions were conducted online due to time constraints, and it was suggested that future iterations of this model incorporate face-to-face teaching to maximise learning connections.

Mentoring model

Benefits of the mentoring model adopted during the project were identified in relation to participants, mentors themselves, and, more broadly, community digital hubs.

Benefits to Participants

Evaluation evidence suggests that the mentor model empowered mentors to make a positive impact within their community groups:

The mentor model allows the message of digital inclusion to be delivered from a different voice or perspective, e.g., young people in school at risk of dropping out needed a different voice than a teacher delivering the message, this is where the community mentor model is most powerful. (QP12)

The model was seen as particularly important for engaging individuals at the margins of digital inclusion:

The life experiences/skills of the mentor that are relatable to the target groups makes the messaging more powerful to hard to reach groups. (QP12)

Mentors worked as trusted points of contact who provided support and reassurance, while offering constructive and actionable feedback: “[Mentors] act as a safety net for any issues / concerns” (QP2) and provide a structure of trusted support that was not available before:

Mentors are seen as peers and not teachers. They are known within their communities and are informal and flexible in delivering set sessions, 1-2-1 and ad hoc advice and support (QP5).

The approach of equipping trusted community members with digital knowledge has facilitated learning and support within and across the community, as well as across generations. In the community digital hubs developed during the project, this emerged as a notable and, in some cases, unexpected outcome of the project:

We have been able to get all ages involved with this. All have gained skills, confidence, and knowledge, and all have enjoyed it. Age integration was brilliant. People who fear tech have played with drones, tried apps / sites they didn't feel sure about and have continued to explore outside of sessions (QP2)

Research vignettes of individual participant cases

Vignette 1: Supporting inclusion through adapted digital learning

LB, a 17-year-old young person involved in Sacriston Youth Project, joined the programme with reported limited digital confidence and additional learning needs linked to dyslexia and autism. Although she could use a smartphone for basic tasks, online safety, recognising trustworthy relationships and completing schoolwork that requires use of digital resources independently was a challenge for her. This often led to anxiety around homework. A turning point for her came when sessions were adapted to meet her needs, using blue paper to make reading easier and breaking tasks down into clear, step-by-step instructions with one-to-one support. Learning how to spot warning signs of unsafe online interactions and how to block or report users was particularly empowering and gave her a strong sense of control. Over time, she has felt more confident as a digital user, attempting tasks before asking for help. Her anxiety reduced noticeably, and successful online experiences boosted her self-esteem. This example demonstrates how digital support can significantly improve confidence and independence for young people, particularly those with additional learning needs. By adapting teaching approaches and accessibility tools, digital inclusion programmes can remove barriers that prevent young people from engaging fully with technology.

Vignette 2: Building confidence and independence in later life

M., an older resident in Stanley involved in the programme through Pact House, was initially extremely anxious about going online, with fears of scams reinforced by negative media coverage. For a long time, he resisted using a mobile phone altogether, but personal needs linked to his mobility and the closure of services in the town meant he felt the need to adapt. Through patient, trust-based mentoring delivered by familiar staff, he slowly began to engage. Over time, he learned to manage online banking, shop safely using platforms he trusted such as Amazon, and even participated in online gaming. These new skills made a tangible difference to his daily life, particularly given the closure of his local bank branch and his limited mobility, reducing costs (e.g. of travelling to other branches) and increasing independence. Mentors noted a visible shift in his confidence and willingness to ask questions without feeling embarrassed. An unexpected outcome from his willingness to learn was the growth of intergenerational learning, as young volunteers within Pact House supported M. and other older adults, strengthening relationships and challenging assumptions about who holds digital expertise. At a wider level, the Pact House digital hub became a vital, welcoming space for residents facing reduced face-to-face services, with trust and local relationships cited as central to its success in reducing isolation and barriers to essential digital access.

Vignette 3: Enabling pathways for a NEET young adult

E. is a 19-year-old care leaver who is currently NEET, having experienced a disrupted education and leaving school with low academic qualifications. At school, he struggled to engage, had limited social interaction, and developed low confidence, challenges that have continued into early adulthood. Living with ADHD, Ethan finds concentration difficult and social situations overwhelming, which has led him to spend a significant amount of time online, where he feels more comfortable connecting through gaming and social media.

Although E. appeared confident navigating digital platforms, before joining the programme, he had little understanding of online safety. He was unsure how to manage privacy settings, identify unsafe or

misleading content, or respond to uncomfortable interactions, leaving him vulnerable online. These gaps also limited his ability to use digital tools to support his aspirations, including his ambition to become a rugby coach.

E. was introduced to the Trusted Connections programme at Kingston Park Stadium, a place that plays a central role in his life. As a familiar, trusted environment where he volunteers regularly, the stadium provided structure, safety, and a strong sense of belonging. Supported by a mentor he already knew, Ethan engaged confidently in tailored sessions. Over time, he developed safer online behaviours, increased confidence, and practical digital skills. He now uses a laptop to create his online CV, apply for jobs, and access training. These are steps that felt out of reach for him only months prior to his engagement with the programme of activities the project offered him.

Benefits to mentors

There were also benefits to the mentors themselves. The mentoring training allowed them to boost their skills and confidence as well as gain a teaching qualification (Level 3) with a reported impact to their own future prospects:

Qualification gives skills to impart information in a safe, inclusive way. (QP10)

The qualification, coupled with the mentor training package, created value for those who volunteered their skills and time to the project in exchange for digital knowledge.

Mentors felt valued and gained satisfaction from making a positive difference. Teaching others reinforced and enhanced their own knowledge. Mentors built relationships, widened their networks, and feel more engaged in their community. (QP9)

Learning within the project was not seen as one-directional; rather, the mentoring model fostered multi-directional exchange, which is fundamental to building trusted relationships grounded in mutuality and shared appreciation. This was evident in the reported interactions between mentors and community members, who demonstrated openness to learning from one another:

Mentors learn from participants too, gaining new perspectives, experiences, and ways of thinking. Having mentors embedded in a project helps create a more supportive, person-centred environment. (...) People are more likely to engage when support comes from someone relatable and approachable, improving overall project outcomes. (QP9)

Research vignettes of individual mentor cases

Vignette 4: Strengthening critical digital awareness through mentoring

P., a mentor with Newcastle Rugby Foundation, came into the project confident in his digital skills and comfortable using online platforms. However, as he took part in the training, he found himself reflecting more deeply on his own habits. Topics such as targeted advertising, subtle misinformation, changing privacy settings and digital wellbeing prompted him to realise that even experienced users can endorse outdated practices or become passive or immune to the familiarity of digital environments. While delivering sessions to young people, P. began revisiting his own privacy settings, became more intentional about managing screen time, and gained an understanding of moderation and reporting tools. He described feeling calmer and more in control of his digital life as a result. What stood out most for P. was seeing the immediate effect on the young people he worked with: they began questioning online content more critically, showed greater awareness of online safety and digital footprints, and used privacy tools more confidently given the advice he could now give. Beyond the sessions, P. found himself supporting colleagues, family members and community groups with safer accounts and device settings, becoming an informal digital advocate within Newcastle Rugby Foundation. The experience illustrated how the Trusted Connections project not only strengthens individual confidence but also builds wider community capacity through trusted relationships.

Vignette 5: From basic user to confident digital mediator

D., a practitioner at Auxillia, initially described herself as a basic digital user who joined the mentoring programme hoping to build confidence rather than expertise. Through the sessions, she became more familiar with the platforms and technologies young people use daily and realised where her own assumptions and knowledge gaps were. This new understanding had an immediate impact on her professional practice, making her feel far more confident giving advice about online behaviour and digital risks. She noticed that conversations with both young people and parents became easier and more constructive, especially around privacy settings and safe digital engagement at home. One particularly significant ‘a-ha’ moment for D. was when, via the programme, she learnt how algorithms shape online experiences; she began making more deliberate choices about what she engaged with, reported or dismissed, and started encouraging others to do the same. She also reflected on how this learning also translated into tailored support for older adults, recognising that many relied solely on smartphones for their online engagement. By adjusting her approach to everyday tasks such as messaging or sharing photos, she was able to offer more inclusive and relevant support. For D., the programme marked a move from passive technology use to intentional digital practices, with benefits felt across multiple community groups she works with.

Benefits of community digital hubs

The development of community digital hubs, underpinned by a network of trained and trusted mentors, has enabled partners to gain renewed prominence for their digital expertise:

We have become a more digital friendly location, with better advice for those who need it (QP3)

Additionally, the mentoring approach established by the project provides a lasting legacy, enabling key messages to continue being shared beyond the duration of the funded programme.

The mentor model was regarded as an invaluable aspect of the project. Benefits to participants, mentors and community hubs were identified in line with the Trusted Connections aims and values, evidenced by participants observations that the mentoring approach fostered “[a] shared sense of community towards digital inclusion (....) ran by the community for the community” (QP10).

Overall, the mentoring approach represents a key success of the project. By investing in local people as knowledge brokers, the Trusted Connections project has created capacity that extends beyond the funded period. This aligns with the perspective endorsed by the project, one in which digital inclusion is regarded as a social process in which learning is relational, iterative, and grounded in shared experience. As seen in practice, the network of trained mentors fostered by Trusted Connections can amplify impact, support learning, and foster digital engagement across different groups.

Community digital hubs and digital upskilling

In addition to the recruitment and training of mentors, and adoption of a mentoring model, another key goal of the project related to the creation of community digital hubs providing the infrastructure required to upskill in excess of 300 participants during the short lifetime of the project.

During the project, all five delivery partners successfully established community digital hubs to enable the delivery of digital skills training via volunteer mentors. Within these Hubs, 113 digital inclusion sessions were delivered, achieving 1380 separate participations from 369 unique participants (many participants attended multiple sessions). Participants represented the following groups:

- Young People
- NEET Young People (or at risk of NEET)
- Adults
- Adults aged 55+

Evaluation evidence demonstrates the effectiveness of the digital skills sessions. Partners and mentors reported that session objectives had been achieved. This finding is mirrored in participant feedback, which demonstrates significant improvements to confidence and skills as a result of the sessions (pre-session baseline skills and confidence versus post-session baseline skills and confidence).

Preliminary session evaluation data indicate clear gains in confidence across groups, with particularly notable shifts among older participants, who are known to be more moderate in their self-reporting. Individuals aged 55+ tended to report lower confidence before the sessions, with most describing themselves as having low or moderate confident levels. Following participation, this distribution shifted more significantly for this group, with the majority reporting having acquired confidence, suggesting meaningful progression for this cohort.

Among younger participants – including NEET group, self-reported confidence levels were already relatively high at the outset, with most reporting being quite confident or confident. After the sessions, this trend consolidated further, with participants moving towards extremely confident levels, indicating reinforcement and consolidation of perceived digital self-confidence.

These patterns point to the sessions’ effectiveness in both building foundational confidence where it was limited and strengthening it where it was already present.

That said, these findings are based on self-reported measures of pre- and post-sessions. The project’s timeframe did not allow for a comprehensive post-evaluation of its longer-term impact. Such follow-up work will be key to enabling a more in-depth and retrospective analysis of learning gains, offering a clearer understanding of how confidence and capability evolved over time beyond the immediate outcomes of the sessions.

Participants reported increased comfort with technology, greater confidence in navigating digital environments, and a stronger sense of agency when engaging online.

Key benefits identified by participants include:

- **Technical and practical skills**

Participants identified clear gains in technical competencies, often framed in terms of overcoming fear or uncertainty around technology. Reported impacts included enhanced understanding of specific tools and devices as well as improved control when using digital interfaces. Comments such as “*touching technology without breaking it*” illustrate how sessions enabled participants to move from apprehension to hands-on engagement, supporting foundational confidence alongside skills acquisition.

- **Wellbeing**

Wellbeing emerged as a key area of impact. Participants described learning strategies to support healthier digital habits, such as managing screen time and disengaging from devices at night, and maintaining healthy online interactions by developing principles for their own approach to digital engagement. This was compounded by observations regarding how the sessions supported participants in developing a more reflective and balanced relationship with technology. Increased confidence in setting boundaries, recognising cyberbullying, and feeling able to “*say no*” further demonstrates how digital inclusion intersected with ideas of safe behaviours, emotional resilience and self-care.

- **Digital safety, privacy, and awareness**

Substantial gains were reported in relation to digital safety and privacy. Participants expressed increased confidence in staying safe online, recognising scams (including AI-generated content), creating stronger passwords, and using security features such as two-step verification. Many demonstrated heightened awareness of privacy settings, data protection, and safe online shopping practices. Participants’ testimonies also showed a move from passive or uncertain engagement to more informed understanding of digital safeguarding approaches.

- **Understanding digital footprints and online presence**

Participants also identified key gains related to learning and reflection about digital footprints and online self-presentation, noting increased awareness of how online content can have long term consequences. Feedback such as “*thinking about what I post online*” illustrates growing critical engagement with digital visibility and personal data, particularly relevant for employability and civic participation.

- **Wider community impact**

Importantly, the impact of the sessions extended beyond individual participants. Evaluation evidence shows that learning was shared with families and members of the community who did not attend sessions. Participants reporting intentions to pass on knowledge about online safety, privacy, and data use to others. This feeding forward approach to how learning is redirected to other meaningful parties shows the project’s broader social value and emphasis on community-based empowerment and trusted relationships.

Limitations

While the project delivered clear benefits, it also highlighted some important learning points, particularly in relation to timeframes. The overall timescale influenced the pace at which activities could be delivered and embedded, especially given the differing needs and capacities of partner organisations and their respective audiences:

My main struggle was the coursework and time frame (QP2)

The timescale of the project was difficult to allow more training on these with the participants in the sessions (QP10)

Partners and mentors noted the value of additional time to further develop and specialise in specific topics, enabling them to build both their own confidence and participants' confidence more gradually. This reflects the broader understanding that developing trust, both in one’s own knowledge and in relationships with others, is an ongoing process that strengthens over time.

Although some mentors found the programme fast-paced, this is balanced by the significant progress and achievements made within a relatively short period. Looking ahead, this experience suggests that initiatives focused on trust building and digital inclusion can benefit from extended timelines, allowing practices, relationships, and local capacity to develop more fully and sustainably.

Key learnings from the Trusted Connections approach

The evaluation evidence shows that Trusted Connections has delivered meaningful outcomes across multiple dimensions, including technical skills, confidence, well-being, digital safety, and a deeper understanding of digital engagement and participation. These findings reinforce the project's central premise: that digital inclusion is most effective when approached as a relational process. In this model, individuals are supported not only to develop technical proficiency but also to engage with digital technologies in ways that are confident, safe, ethical, and relevant to their everyday lives and community contexts.

A key learning from the project is the importance of time. Building digital confidence and establishing effective mentoring relationships cannot be rushed. Trust develops gradually and must align with the rhythms and realities of the communities involved. The project highlighted that engagement with trusted parties is essential for enabling deeper learning, fostering meaningful connections, and supporting change.

Another important insight concerns the flow of digital cultural knowledge within the partnership. Knowledge did not move in a simple top-down direction; rather, it circulated between expert partners (university to trainers of mentors) and those working directly in community settings. This exchange was characterised by both rigour and care, combining expertise with contextual understanding and sensitivity to local needs. As a result, the Trusted Connections approach aims to develop learning environments in which knowledge can be co-developed, adapted, and embedded in practice in ways that are both effective and sustainable.

Additionally, in a rapidly evolving digital landscape, it is important to recognise that digital inclusion is not a fixed endpoint but a moving target, requiring continuous learning and sustained engagement with emerging technologies and practices. As digital systems, platforms, and governance structures develop, so too must the capacities and understanding of individuals, communities, and organisations. This means that digital inclusion work is necessarily ongoing. As community members become more confident and sophisticated in their digital practices, there is a corresponding need to engage with more complex and critical forms of digital knowledge. This includes, but is not limited to, areas such as artificial intelligence, algorithmic decision making, data ethics, platform governance, and the social consequences of automated systems.

Addressing these challenges requires an ecosystem-based approach that values both expert knowledge and lived experience. Maintaining strong partnerships with universities and research institutions is therefore essential, as they bring critical expertise, interdisciplinary insight, and the capacity to analyse emerging digital trends. Equally important is deep collaboration with communities, whose lived experience of digital forms of engagement offers contextual understandings of how technologies are encountered, negotiated, and resisted in everyday life. Bridging these forms of knowledge enables more responsive, ethical, and inclusive digital practices, thus ensuring that digital inclusion remains adaptive, relational, and focused on people's needs.

Creating infrastructures of opportunity: A blueprint for digital inclusion

The concept of “infrastructures of digital opportunity”¹ frames digital inclusion beyond short-term interventions to more systemic, relational, and sustainable approaches to digital inclusion. Rather than viewing digital skills as isolated competencies, this approach recognises that meaningful inclusion depends on interconnected systems of access, trust, knowledge, and community participation through mentors and community support.

To share key learnings formed throughout the project, a blueprint for digital inclusion has been developed. This blueprint is based on a pedagogy of empowerment grounded in trust, place, and participation. It can be adapted by other organisations aiming to adopt a more relational approach, one that empowers community members to engage meaningfully and confidently in digital spaces.

At its core, this blueprint is underpinned by four interrelated pillars: access, digital literacies, agency, and inclusive participation. These pillars demonstrate that digital inclusion is not solely about providing devices or connectivity, but about creating the conditions in which individuals can confidently engage, create, and collaborate within digital environments.

This blueprint positions digital inclusion as a social justice and civic engagement project, rooted in community action and local context, rather than a purely technical and/or skills based intervention. The Trusted Connections project addressed persistent regional inequalities in the North East of England by foregrounding agency, trust, participation, and place-based knowledge as foundations for ethical and sustainable digital engagement. This blueprint is designed to support careful adaptation to the specific needs of other local and regional contexts.

The core vision of this blueprint, which we have developed through the project, is one in which digitally included communities are those where people can engage with digital technologies not only confidently, but also critically, safely, and at their own pace. This engagement is supported by trusted relationships and locally grounded infrastructures that create and sustain digital opportunity for everyone. Building confidence in digital environments, particularly among those historically excluded, requires time, consistency, and meaningful engagement with its people. Trust operates at multiple levels: trust in technology, in one’s own abilities, and in the people and organisations providing support. Projects that prioritise these relational dimensions are better positioned to foster sustained participation and long-term change.

¹ The term “infrastructures of digital opportunity” is inspired by Dr Fiona Hill’s concept of “infrastructures of opportunity,” which emphasises the social, institutional, and relational conditions that enable individuals and communities to realise their potential. Building on this idea, infrastructures of digital opportunity aims to point out the importance of creating supportive digital ecosystems, encompassing digital access, skills, agency and participation, as a way to enable meaningful and equitable digital engagement.

Blueprint of digital inclusion core principles

The blueprint is underpinned by six interrelated principles drawn from the Trusted Connections project:

1. **Relational, rather than deficit based:** digital exclusion is not a “lack of something to be fixed” but a condition shaped by social, cultural, economic, and historical factors that can be tackled.
2. **Trust as infrastructure:** Trust in mentors, community organisations, platforms, and institutions is as critical as broadband connectivity or digital skills. It is the glue of meaningful learning.
3. **Place-based and community-led learning:** digital practices are shaped by local histories, material conditions, and social networks. Inclusion is best cultivated with communities, rather than delivered to them.
4. **Pedagogy of empowerment:** digital literacies are forms of informed agency, developed through dialogue and discussion, reflection and deliberation, and participation and creation rather than through the simple transformation of information, rules and skills. Digital inclusion relies on first-hand experience by all parties involved.
5. **Sustained support:** Short-term, transactional provision is insufficient. Digital confidence and agency develop over time, at different paces, in line with community needs.
6. **Ethical and critical engagement:** digital inclusion requires an understanding of how digital environments shape power, (e.g., who it can empower and disempower and how). It demands an appreciation of the mediation of risk, enabling participation as well as opportunity.

Building a sustainable community-based network of mentors

Mentors are central to delivery and sustainability of digital inclusion. Mentors as “meaningful others”:

- Are embedded within trusted communities and/or organisations;
- Provide support to community members over time;
- Model sound, ethical digital practices;
- Ensure digital inclusion within community settings can be sustained over time.

The mentor network functions as a living infrastructure for digital inclusion with the purpose of creating a ripple effect, i.e., of

**Digital inclusion
blueprint - 6
interconnected
principles:**

- 1- relational and
community-
led
approaches,**
- 2- Trust as
essential
infrastructure,**
- 3- Place-based
learning**
- 4- Empowerment**
- 5- Sustained
long-term
support**
- 6- Ethical and
critical
engagement**

individuals moving from mentee to mentor leading to the growth of the mentor network within community settings.

Curriculum design

Rather than a fixed curriculum, the blueprint outlined above promotes a flexible framework of resources for both mentor training and use with community members. This includes the development of:

- Modular lesson plans designed based on shared values, and
- Learning activities which can be developed across audiences and contexts.

This flexibility ensures legitimacy, relevance, and community ownership.

Delivery model

Digital inclusion is achieved through the effort of the whole community network rather than via isolated interventions.

The network brings together:

- People (community members, mentors, practitioners)
- Technologies (devices, platforms, connectivity)
- Spaces (digital community hubs)
- Resources

Based on the blueprint shared above, future projects may consider creating infrastructures of digital opportunity, which involve:

- Designing interventions that integrate access, skills, confidence, and participation;
- Co-producing knowledge within trusted community contexts;
- Investing in local capacity through mentoring and peer networks;
- Building cross sector partnerships that support meaningful and sustained impact;
- Allowing sufficient time for relationships, trust, and practices to develop.

“Digital inclusion is achieved through the effort of the whole community network rather than via isolated interventions.”

This blueprint seeks to move beyond generic, top-down approaches to digital inclusion and instead embraces a model of digital empowerment that supports informed agency through trusted relationships and community networks. It also reframes “hard to reach” groups as historically underserved communities that warrant sustained and coordinated support, including access to technical equipment, mentorship, shared knowledge and resources, and meaningful connections to community serving partners such as higher education institutions and social enterprises. In essence, digital inclusion is not an individual responsibility but a shared civic duty grounded in solidarity and collective action

Conclusion

The Trusted Connections project, while short and fast-paced, was successful pilot of community focused and community driven digital inclusion. Key project goals and KPIs were achieved, with 27 mentors trained and five community digital hubs developed. In total, 369 individuals within communities benefited from one or more of the 113 digital inclusion sessions which saw 1380 participations. Feedback from partners, mentors, mentor trainers and participants is overwhelmingly positive. Measurable improvements to confidence and digital skills were observed via pre- and post-session participant feedback and through focus groups.

Yet the real successes of the project lie not in those achievements listed above (although they are also worth celebrating), but in the sustainable and scalable approach developed through the project.

The approach adopted here provides a real example of effective practice, illustrating the benefits of moving away from brief, transactional interventions toward longer-term approaches that prioritise continuity and personable engagement. The Trusted Connections project offers a scalable and adaptable way to address digital exclusion, one that aims to be equitable, sustainable, and grounded in the lived realities of communities. Rather than relying on short-term, fragmented interventions, the project seeks to cultivate long-lasting infrastructures of digital opportunity. This involves documenting and strengthening networks of practice, shared values, and local expertise, ensuring that digital inclusion efforts can continue beyond the project's life.

The development of a Mentor Digital Literacies Diagnostic Tool, a flexible curriculum blueprint, and a network of trained mentors

“Digital inclusion is not an individual responsibility but a shared civic duty grounded in solidarity and collective action.”

contributes to this sustainability, providing resources and capacity that can be adapted and used by organisations across the region and beyond.

The project also contributes to broader academic and policy debates about digital inclusion. By foregrounding relationality, trust, and community-based learning, it challenges dominant narratives that equate digital inclusion with access or employability. It advances a conceptualisation of digital inclusion as an emancipatory practice, one that enables individuals and communities to shape their digital experiences collectively and ethically. This aligns with emerging scholarship that emphasises the importance of critical engagement, reflexivity, and co-production in digital literacies education.

Furthermore, the project's place-based approach highlights the importance of local knowledge and cultural context in shaping digital practices. Digital engagement is not uniform; it is shaped by the material, social, and institutional environments in which individuals live. By grounding digital inclusion efforts in local contexts, the project ensures that learning is meaningful, relevant, and connected to lived realities. This approach enhances the legitimacy and appeal of digital inclusion initiatives, fostering greater engagement and more sustainable outcomes.

In summary, the Trusted Connections project situates digital inclusion within a broader socio-cultural and structural context, recognising that meaningful digital participation requires more than access or technical skills. It requires trust, relational support, critical awareness, and the capacity to navigate digital environments in ways that align with one's values, needs, and aspirations. By advancing a pedagogy of empowerment and embedding digital learning within community-based infrastructures, the project offers a robust and innovative model for addressing digital inequalities in the North East and beyond. Its emphasis on relationality, sustainability, and informed agency positions it as a significant contribution to both academic scholarship and practical digital inclusion efforts.

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